

[CHECK CLOSED CAPTIONS, HIDE CLOSED CAPTIONS, SHOW FULL TRANSCRIPT]

Preamble/ Introduction

Thank you so much for volunteering to interview with us this afternoon.

[mirroring FogNet introductory info below]

Before we get started, I want to check in with you about the consent form I sent you. Did you have any questions or need more time to review it? ● Do we have your consent for being interviewed? And for recording the interview? Great! I'm going to repeat those two questions once we're recording so we have a record of you giving us consent. ● **[PRESS RECORD]** Do we have your consent for being interviewed? And for recording the interview? Thank you, and just so you know, you're free to strike anything you want from the record during the interview and all the way up until we publish the results. So don't hesitate to contact me if you have anything you would like to add or change.

Today we're going to be talking about cold-stunning events, when water temperatures reach threatening levels for wildlife. We're interested in hearing about how you make decisions ahead and during these events and the impacts they may cause as well as hearing about your thoughts on the cold-stunning model and how you and your organization use it during cold-stunning events. I'll be asking about some of the information you use when preparing for these events, like forecast information and model predictions.

This interview has a total of seven sections. As you answer the following questions within each section, it's important that you know that there are no right or wrong answers, and your responses will be most helpful to us if they are what you really think.

You ready? Great!

Research Area 1:

RQ1a:

First, I'll be asking some brief questions about your job and your overall responsibilities **in the first section of the interview.**

Job role and responsibilities

1. Can you tell me about your job, current position, and some of your core responsibilities?

Cold-Stunning Risk, Organizational Cold-Stunning Workflow, and Organizational Role

Now I'd like to shift topics and discuss how you and your group prepare for cold-stunning events and what this type of risk means to you.

2. How do you define a "cold-stunning event" and do you use any other term or phrase for these particular events?
 - a. What kinds of risks, if any, do cold-stunning events pose to you and your organization?

Informational Needs and Organizational Cold-Stunning Workflow

3. Now we're moving on to **the second section**, where we'll talk about the information you rely on and how your organization prepares for cold-stunning events. How do you

typically learn that a cold-stunning event could occur? [Like any specific events, sources, or pieces of information that you can remember.](#)

- a. [\[If not mentioned\]](#) What are the key indicators or factors that may suggest a cold-stunning event may be occurring or approaching?
 - b. [\[If not mentioned\]](#) Where do you typically get your information from? Anywhere else?
 - i. [\[If mention Tissot email\]](#) You mentioned Dr. Tissot's email as a source of information that you use to prepare for cold-stunning events. When considering his emails *leading up to the event*, is there any key information that you find most helpful or find yourself tending to use, need, or look for when planning for response or recovery leading up to or during freeze events?
 1. Is there any information that you remember that you find less useful or not particularly valuable when making decisions regarding response or recovery leading up to or during freeze events?
 2. Is there anything that you remember that could be improved, added, or adjusted to the *cold-stunning advisory guidance sent by email* to help with your decision-making process?
 - ii. [\[If mention other tools/resources and Tissot email\]](#) You mentioned [XXX], what about this information is most useful or find yourself tending to use, need, or look for you when preparing for cold-stunning event risks?
 1. Is there any information from this [tool/message/model] that you find less useful or not particularly valuable when making decisions regarding response or recovery leading up to or during freeze events?
 2. Is there anything that you can remember that could be improved, added, or adjusted to this [tool/message/model] to help with your decision-making process?
 - iii. [\[If mention other tools/resources but no Tissot email\]](#) I'm curious. Are you on Dr. Tissot's cold-stunning advisory email list? (or do you receive Dr. Tissot's cold-stunning advisory emails?)
 1. Is that something that you use?
 - a. [\[Proceed to 3ii questions\]](#)
4. When there is a chance that a cold-stunning event may occur, what actions do you and your organization take, if any, leading up to and during the event?
 - a. Is there a specific area along the Texas coast that you tend to focus your efforts on during cold-stunning events?
 - b. [I'm interested in how your information use changes or doesn't change throughout the time leading up to and during cold stunning events.](#) Does the use of some of these products that you mentioned [\[if mentioned Tissot's email, "along with Dr. Tissot's email"\]](#) change during the course of the cold-stunning event? [For example, from 10 days out, to 5 days, to 1 day before the event? And then during the event itself?](#)

Cold-Stunning Communication Pathways

5. **Awesome, let's move on to the third section.** Are there any key people or groups that you communicate with leading up to and/or during these events? They could be internal or external to your organization.
 - a. What are the key purposes of these communications? Or some of the key messaging points or goals of these exchanges with these groups?
 - b. **[If they mention reaching out]** You mentioned you reach out to [XXX]. Is there a specific point in time leading up to or during a cold-stunning event when you reach out to them?
 - c. **[If they mention people reaching out to them]** You mentioned [XXX] reach/es out to you. Is there a specific point in time leading up to or during the cold-stunning event when they reach out to you?
 - d. Do you or any of your partners have a preferred form of communicating? **This can include emails, phone calls, conference or video meetings.**
 - e. What are some of the challenges you face when communicating during cold-stunning events?

RQ1b:

Success and Challenges

6. **Now moving forward to the fourth section.** Looking back on some of the previous cold-stunning events you've experienced, how do you decide if you and your organization successfully managed it?
 - a. **[If not mentioned/if they struggle]** What factors or points are important to you in assessing if an event was "successful"? **For example, any specific outcomes, actions, or feedback that you expect or look for to determine success.**
 - b. **[If they talk only about the 'environment']** What about with respect to communication and decision-making for the events?
7. Can you now think back to an event that posed more of a challenge for you and your organization?
 - a. **[If not mentioned]** What factors or points do you consider when assessing if an event was "challenging"?
 - b. **[If they talk only about the 'environment']** What about with respect to communication and decision-making for the events?

Research Area 2:

RQ2b:

Interpretation and Use of Current CS Model

Now in this [fifth section of the interview](#), I want to shift gears a bit and talk about the cold-stunning model that's used to inform the cold-stunning advisory emails from Philippe Tissot.

8. Are you familiar with the cold-stunning model referenced in Dr. Tissot's emails?
 - a. [If yes] Great, next we will be moving on towards a portion of the interview where you will be going through different pieces of information that will display various water temperature predictions from this model, and I'd like you to answer some of the following questions I have for you on some of these predictions as best as you can.
 - b. [If no] No problem. Dr. Tissot, an expert scientist at the Conrad Blucher Institute at Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi, currently uses a model that is available online that outputs predictions of water temperatures in the Laguna Madre. He has been using this model for almost 15 years to provide cold-stunning advisory information to the TCRC. For the next portion of the interview, I will direct you to different pieces of information that will display various cold-stunning predictions from this model, and I'd like you to answer some of the following questions I have for you on some of these predictions as best as you can.

CS SIMULATION DECK SET UP: Sharing the slides and getting started with screen sharing

To help with this discussion, I'll send you a link to a slide deck that has more information and visuals. [Interviewer copies link and pastes it into the chat: [CS Simulation \(2024 ex.: V9 0918 w3\).pptx](#)].

Please click on that link in the chat and share your full screen so we can see what you see. [allow time for them to get set up. If needed "You can do this by clicking on the green "Share" button on the bottom of your screen and selecting "full screen" so that you are able to share your entire desktop screen that displays the slide deck I just sent, and then click "Share"].

Awesome! It will also be helpful to hide the floating Zoom meeting panel as well so it doesn't block any information you're looking at on these slides. You can do this by going to the Zoom black panel on the top of your screen, pressing on the three dots labeled "More" and clicking "Hide Floating Meeting Controls."

Great! Now please stay on the first slide here and put the slides in presentation mode by clicking on the "Present" button in the top right corner.

SET UP FOR PRACTICE TASK

Step 1: Introducing the practice task

Alrighty, great. For this task, I'm interested in your thoughts and interpretations on some of the model outputs that are used to inform about incoming cold-stunning threats. You'll see two models: one that predicts water temperatures in the Laguna Madre (or the cold-stunning model) and one that predicts air temperatures from The Weather Company.

Step 2: Explaining practice task and what to do

Before we dive into the main activity, I've prepared a short practice round with an example that uses only one day's worth of water and air temperature prediction information. We're using it as an easy, familiar example for the practice task to help you get the hang of using what we refer to as the "*cold-stunning simulation slidedeck*."

Step 3: Describing the cold-stunning event simulation deck and predictive panels

Now for the practice task, you're seeing the first day within the "cold-stunning simulation slidedeck" titled **December 13th: Cold-Stunning Predictive Panel**. This slide is referred to as a "*predictive panel*." On the left, you'll see the model outputs for that day, and on the right, there's a checklist of tasks and questions to guide you through the slidedeck, task, and questions to consider, mainly focusing on your interpretation of the model outputs and your thoughts on the likelihood of the threshold being crossed. I'll pause here for a moment to give you some time to review this slide.

Step 4: Describing the daily predictive panel sets

[Wait for 5 seconds and ask] Great, now when you're ready, click on the top image on the left, and we'll walk through it together.

Within this slide, you're now seeing the Cold-Stunning Model's water temperature predictions. You'll find orange text pointing out the locations of the checklist, legends for the models, and links to help you navigate either back to the predictive panel or to the remaining prediction information. These navigation links are labeled in green and can find them either in the checklist to move forward or on the top left of the slide to move backward. Just take a quick moment to glance at this slide; you don't need to interpret it—just familiarize yourself with the layout. Once you're ready, click on the green link in the checklist to move forward.

[Wait for 5-10 seconds] Awesome, you'll find similar information here, however for The Weather Company's air temperature predictions. Take a brief look at this slide as well—again, no need to dive into the details. After a few seconds, click the green link in the checklist to go back to the December 13th predictive panel, and we'll move on to the practice round.

Step 5: Stop and check in about the slidedeck and task

Awesome. Does this set-up make sense? Do you have any questions?

TRANSITION TO THE THINK ALOUD DESCRIPTION

Now before we go ahead with the practice task there's one more thing I'm going to add: thinking aloud.

THINK ALOUD INTRODUCTION

Step 1: Introducing the "think aloud"

Specifically, I'd like you to think aloud while you explore the information and review the Checklist items- sharing whatever is going through your mind. It's essentially like talking to yourself when working through a tricky math problem or puzzle. Again, please use the Checklist on each of the slides as a guide when reviewing the sets of information.

Step 2: Stop and check in about thinking aloud

Does thinking aloud make sense? Do you have any questions? We can even quickly walk-through the task together to get the hang of it if you'd like.

[if they want to walk-through, follow along, giving them any clarifying instructions if necessary]
[if they don't want to walk-through, "Sounds good!"]

START PRACTICE TASK

Step 1: Putting the task and think aloud together

Great, now we're going to combine thinking aloud with the practice task to get used to thinking out loud and reviewing the predictive panels at the same time.

To set the stage for this activity:

Imagine that it's December of 2025, Dr. Tissot is currently out of town and is not able to send out advisory information and guidance. However, the cold-stunning model is still up and operational, along with air temperature predictions from The Weather Company. I'd like to hear your thoughts and interpretations on some of the model outputs and how you would use them to make decisions for the potential cold-stunning event.

Please review the information on the predictive panel by clicking the images on the left and do your best when answering the questions listed on the Checklist. **Remember**, once you feel you've finished answering these questions, return to the predictive panel by clicking on the green link labeled Predictive Panel, and I will ask a few more questions before we move forward.

Remember to think out loud as you go. There are no wrong answers and you can always ask us not to report something. Do you have any questions?

Awesome. We'll turn off our videos so you can focus on the task and thinking aloud.

Please begin when you're ready and let us know when you're done.

PRACTICE THINK ALOUD

[Let them explore and **only prompt with "what's going through your mind" if they go silent for 15-30 seconds**. Wait for them to say they're done]

That was great, very well done. [Give any feedback that is needed - talk more, less explaining, etc.] Now we'll move on to the main activity. Any questions before we continue? Great!

MAIN THINK ALOUD - CS Simulation Information board

Now I'm going to ask you to review a few other predictive panels just like you did for the practice example. And the task is the same. ~~To start, remember that Dr. Tissot is currently out of town and cannot send out advisory information and guidance of his interpretation of the model outputs. However, the cold-stunning model is still operational, along with air temperature predictions from The Weather Company.~~ As you go through each predictive panel, remember to think aloud and answer the questions on the checklist. Once you've answered the questions, return to the predictive panel slide that you're working on and we'll walk through some follow-up questions, like I noted before.

Do you have any questions before we start?

Great! Please click the link on the bottom right of the slide to move on to the next predictive panel. You should see the December 16th Predictive Panel.

Awesome - Just to give you some context, this information was curated for a simulated cold front in 2025. This is not a real event; it's a hypothetical scenario designed for our analysis. We're collecting feedback to help inform the development of new cold-stunning information for the TCRC. And just a note, no need to hold back on your responses or worry about us! Your honest feedback is exactly what we need to improve our model predictions and how we communicate inferences on the cold stunning event threat. No hard feelings on our end!

And by the way, if you accidentally move too far ahead in the slidedeck, you can use the red "Help" button on the bottom left of the predictive panel slide to navigate back to the correct predictive panel. Again, we'll turn off our videos so you can focus on the task and thinking aloud. Please begin when you're ready and let us know when you're done.

FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS FOR MAIN THINK ALOUD

[Ask these questions for each predictive panel set on the CS simulation slidedeck.]

[for December 16th]

That was great, very well done. [Give any feedback that is needed - talk more, less explaining, etc.] Let's move on to some of the follow-up questions for this predictive panel:

9. **MODEL INTERPRETATION QUESTIONS:** [if they answered yes to the threshold being crossed]
 - a. You noted that you believed the threshold was going to be crossed, can you tell me when you think it will be crossed and why? Feel free to click on the images too!
 - i. [if they ask for clarification on timing, state "Start with the whole panel and if there is a specific time that you're interested in, let me know that too!"]
 - b. How long do you think this event might last? And why?
 - c. Based on the information provided, can you tell me what you believe the possible lowest water temperatures will be? Why?
10. **TRUST QUESTIONS:** [if they answered no to the threshold being crossed, move on to TRUST questions]
 - a. As presented, would you say that you trust this information?
 - i. [If yes] Why is that? What about this information makes you trust it?
 - ii. [If no] Why is that? Would anything help you trust this information?
 1. [if they mention Tissot with no context or reasoning] Thank you for mentioning Dr. Tissot's emails. Can you point out any particular information from those emails that you would be looking for or wanting to see?
11. **USE QUESTIONS:** Great, thank you for sharing that. Now, with all the information you've gone over, what would your next steps be?
 - a. If the TCRC decided to issue an advisory - meaning dredging and navigation activity in the Laguna Madre would be voluntarily interrupted - would you support the decision and why?

Awesome. Please proceed to the next predictive panel by clicking on the bottom right that says "Click Here to the Next Forecast" and let me know when you are done!

[After first Predictive Panel “December 16th” and move on to “December 19th”, ask these questions instead]

Alright, thank you. [Give any feedback that is needed - talk more, less explaining, etc.] Let’s move on to the follow-up questions for this predictive panel:

[for December 19th]

12. **MODEL INTERPRETATION QUESTIONS:** [if they answered yes to the threshold being crossed]
 - a. You noted that you believed the threshold was going to be crossed, can you tell me when you think the threshold will be crossed and how long you think the cold-stunning event will last? Feel free to click on the images too!
 - i. [if they ask for clarification on timing, state “Start with the whole panel and if there is a specific time that you’re interested in, let me know that too!”]
 - b. Based on the information provided, can you tell me what you believe the possible lowest water temperatures will be? Why?
13. **TRUST QUESTIONS:** [if they answered they didn’t trust the December 16th information]
 - a. [if they said they trusted the information] You said you trusted this information before, are there any updates to your trust in this information? And why?
 - i. [if they mention PT with no context or reasoning] Thank you for mentioning Dr. Tissot’s emails. Can you point out any particular information from those emails that you would be looking for or wanting to see?
 - ii. [if they say their trust lowered] Why is that? Would anything help you trust this information?
14. **USE QUESTIONS:** Great, thank you for sharing that. Now, with all the information you’ve gone over, what would your next steps be?
 - a. If the TCRC decided to issue an advisory, would you support the decision and why? [Stop asking this question after December 19th Predictive Panel]

Awesome. Please proceed to the last predictive panel and let me know when you are done!

[for December 21st]

15. **MODEL INTERPRETATION QUESTIONS:**
 - i. Now that the threshold has officially been crossed, can you tell me when you think the threshold will be crossed coming out of the event and how long you think the cold-stunning event will last?
 - ii. Based on the information provided, can you tell me what you believe the possible lowest water temperatures will be? Why?
16. **TRUST QUESTIONS:** [if they answered they didn’t trust the December 16th information]
 - a. [if they said they trusted the information] You said you trusted this information before, are there any updates to your trust in this information? And why?
 - i. [if they mention PT with no context or reasoning] Thank you for mentioning Dr. Tissot’s emails. Can you point out any particular information from those emails that you would be looking for or wanting to see?
 - ii. [if they say their trust lowered] Why is that? Would anything help you trust this information?

17. **USE QUESTIONS:** Great, thank you for sharing that. Now, with all the information you've gone over, what would your next steps be?

CS SIMULATION FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS

Thank you so much. That was great.

18. Based on the information presented, is there anything else you would add, remove, adjust, or improve to help with your decision-making process?
19. We've talked a lot about the various people and organizations you rely on, as well as the information and tools you use to prepare for cold-stunning events. Given these resources, how do you assess what is trustworthy when making decisions about managing the potential risks of cold-stunning events?
- What features or details do you think are important when it comes to trustworthiness?
 - [if time] Is there anything that was not included in the slide deck that might affect how much you trust the information you receive during these events?
20. And just to dig a little deeper, what does the term "trustworthy" mean to you in this context?
- [if they struggle] Feel free to share anything about the model itself, how we communicate cold-stunning advisories, your workflow and network, TCRC consensus, or really anything else that comes to mind.

UNCERTAINTY VISUALIZATION INTEGRATION ACTIVITY

Thank you so much for sharing this with us. We are now at the [sixth section](#) and I have one more batch of information for you to explore before we wrap things up. Thank you for remaining patient throughout this process with us.

In a moment, you will see additional water temperature prediction information for a *different* hypothetical cold-stunning event than what you were reviewing before. **So let's now click on the green link to move on to the Additional Water Temperature Information at the bottom right of the slide** [[Additional Water Temperature Prediction Information](#)].

On this slide are visuals that depict the same water temperature information but are presented in three different ways. In a moment, I'd like you to review each one by either clicking on the images or the green links beside them, thinking aloud as you interpret what you're seeing.

There's no checklist here; again, just share your initial thoughts, noting any visuals you find useful or less helpful for decision-making during cold-stunning events, and explain why. Please note that these visuals account only for the sea turtle threshold, not the fishery threshold.

Do you have any questions before we start? Awesome. Again, we'll turn off our videos so you can focus on the task and thinking aloud. Please begin when you're ready and let us know when you're done.

[Allow time for interpretation of images. Once interviewee has completed Uncertainty Slides...]

Thank you for this!

21. Based on the information presented, was there any set of information that was most helpful or confusing when understanding the risk of the cold-stunning event occurring?
22. Is there anything else you would add, remove, adjust, or improve to help with your decision-making process?
23. With the information provided, can you tell me when you think an advisory should be issued?

RQ2a:

Perceptions of AI/ML

Thank you so much, this has been extremely helpful. **We are now at the seventh and final section of the interview** and I just have a few more specific questions about the current cold-stunning model before we wrap up. You can stop sharing your screen now.

24. When communicating with others within your office/organization/agency about the cold-stunning model, how do you describe what it is?
25. When you hear the terms artificial intelligence and/or machine learning, what comes to mind?
26. Interesting thank you. I'd like to share that the cold-stunning model that we've been discussing is based on AI/ML techniques. Now knowing that the model is based on AI/ML, does this affect your level of trust in the cold-stunning advisory information? Why or why not?

Closing

27. **Awesome thanks.** Now is there anything you think we missed or anything that you would like to add?

Alright! Thank you so much again for participating in this interview with us! This has been extremely helpful for our study and our team. **To ensure we gather the most authentic experiences from everyone, I kindly ask that you keep our conversation and the materials we discussed just between us for now.** I'll be in touch when it's okay to chat about the interview with your fellow TCRC members. Thanks so much for this. Enjoy the rest of your day and again if you have any questions or concerns please don't hesitate to reach out to me. Have a great day!

[CHECK CLOSED CAPTIONS, SAVE TRANSCRIPT]